

EFFECT OF IMPREGNATION OF PITCH-DERIVED CARBON COMPOSITES WITH POLYSILOXANE-BASED PRECERAM ON THEIR MICROSTRUCTURE, MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND OXIDATION RESISTANCE

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ABSTRACT

New pitch-based C/C composites were obtained from domestic pitches. These composites were impregnated with different polysiloxane-based solutions of preceram and subjected to heat treatment up to 1700°C. Microstructure, mechanical properties and oxidation resistance of the composites were investigated.

Keywords: carbon/carbon composites, carbon/carbon/ceramic composites, pitch, polysiloxanes, precerams

Introduction

The rapidly developing materials science seeks new structural materials for advanced, high temperature industrial applications. Carbon/carbon composites (C/C) modified with ceramic phases fulfill requirements for such applications, due to their specific thermal and mechanical properties, e.g. oxidation resistance, anisotropy of thermal conductivity, high strength, stiffness and wear resistance. Because of their high manufacturing costs these materials are not yet widely used.

The aim of this work was to investigate impregnation process of pitch-derived C/C composites. C/C composites were obtained from domestic coal-derived isotropic pitches. Composites were impregnated with commercially available polysiloxane-based solutions of preceram. Pitch and polysiloxane substrates used in experiments were inexpensive (cost about 10\$/kg). Microstructure, mechanical properties and oxidation resistance of the composites were investigated.

Materials and methods

M40J carbon fibers (Torayca) and domestic isotropic pitch were used. The unidirectionally-reinforced composite samples were manufactured and then subjected to thermal treatment at 1000°C in an inert atmosphere. C/C composites obtained in such a way were impregnated either with pure Lukosil 901 polysiloxane resin produced by

Lucebni zavody, Kolin (Czech Republic) or with the resin contained silicon carbide powder. Samples were subjected to subsequent thermal treatment up to 1700°C. To determine mechanical parameters, the composite samples were investigated in three points bending test. From strain-force relationships the strength and Young's modulus were calculated. On the basis of results obtained in static loading conditions, parameters of dynamic test were set up. After that, fatigue experiments were carried out. Oxidation resistance of the samples was determined by mass losses of composites heated in air atmosphere at 600°C, for 2 h. The porosity was measured by mercury-porosimeter. Carbon-carbon composites without impregnation were used as a reference.

Resume

No significant differences relevant to mechanical properties in static conditions between C/C reference samples and C/C samples modified with pure polymer were observed. Bending strength for all samples varied from 412 to 480 MPa, and Young's modulus - from 87 to 140 GPa (Figures 1 and 2). Impregnation of C/C samples with polymer contained SiC powder improves their mechanical properties – bending strength increases as compared with C/C samples modified with pure polymer.

Figure 1. Bending strength of investigated composites

Figure 2. Young's modulus of investigated composites

Changes in microstructure of composites before and after impregnation were registered (Table 1). Changes in their microstructure were correlated with the procedure of densification. The impregnation-heat treatment distinctly increased density of composites.

Table 1. Porosity and density of samples

Sample		Porosity [%]	Apparent density [g/cm ³]	Specific density [g/cm ³]
Reference	1 C/C	20.89	1.33	1.68
C/C/ceramic composites	2 C/C + resin, HT 1000°C	10.93	1.52	1.71
	3 C/C open pores + resin, HT 1000°C	25.54	1.62	2.18
	4 C/C + resin HT 1000°C + (resin + SiC HT 1000°C)	7.25	1.92	2.07
	5 C/C+ resin, HT 1700°C	20.36	1.52	1.91

The C/C composites after impregnation exhibited better fatigue properties in comparison to pure C/C composites – C/C/ceramic composites displayed 3-4 times higher number of cycles until destruction than the reference samples (Table 2). The applied densification procedure enhanced significantly oxidation resistance of composite samples, especially in case of samples 4 (2-step densification) and 5 (HT 1700°C) (Figure 3).

Table 2. Fatigue resistance measured for C/C and C/C/ceramic composites

SAMPLE	NUMBERS OF CYCLES UNTIL DESTRUCTION
1	110 000
2	450 000
5	300 000

Figure 3. Mass losses of composites after oxidation

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